

D5.2 REPORTS ON DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

SEEDS

VERSION V.5

VERSION CONTROL SHEET

- Project summary**

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DISCLAIMER

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CoR	Gemeente Rotterdam
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam
HUA	Charokopeio Panepistimio
ECSA	Verein Der Europaeischen Burgerwissenschaften - ECSA E.V.
IISPV	Fundació Institut d'Investigació Sanitària Pere Virgili
SEEDS	Science Engagement to Empower Disadvantaged Adolescents
SwafS	Science with and for Society
UOE	University of Exeter

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

SEEDS (Science Engagement to Empower aDolescentS) is a science project by teenagers for teenagers. It aims to empower them to live healthy lifestyles and to help them explore how important and exciting science is. We adopted the extreme citizen science approach, based on the participation of leader 'adolescents in all the research process: identifying adolescents' barriers and necessities for having a healthy lifestyles, designing a community-based public intervention for adolescents of low-socioeconomic areas and with stakeholders' participation, interpretation of the data and dissemination to community. New experiments for healthy lifestyles were created and run in schools in Spain, the Netherlands, Greece and the UK during the first six months of 2022.

The role of targeted and clear communication and dissemination is fundamental to the success of any project. Stakeholders in academia, industry, government, journalists, non-scientific publics and beyond should hear relevant information about the project at the right time and understand how it influences and relates to their work or interests.

In this final report we summarise the original **dissemination** and **communication** strategy of SEEDS and present the key **messages**, target **audiences** and **tools** (chapter 2 [The Dissemination and Communication Strategy in a nutshell](#)). Then we give an overview of the [online presence](#) of SEEDS on Twitter and the activity on the website.

Three [campaigns](#) were carried out for three different audiences: **teachers and educators**, **social workers** and **health professionals** and **teens**. The [final exchange meeting](#) held in Leuven near Brussels on October 18, 2022, is presented at length.

The list of **events and conferences** where SEEDS was presented and represented is available in chapter

SEEDS has also produced relevant **scientific results** that have been published or are being published in [international journals](#).

The dissemination and communication actions, together with the exploitation and sustainability plan, can allow SEEDS to become a model for other operators in the sector or similar sectors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Empowering **teenagers** in health issues and engaging them with **STEM** (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) subjects is the main goal of SEEDS and connects many of the United Nations (UN)'s **Sustainable Development Goals**. This has become even more urgent during the COVID-19 global pandemic where there has been so much disruption to formal education and to teenagers' home lives. To ensure the SEEDS project achieves this goal, a clear Dissemination and Communication Strategy was developed (D5.1 in month 3) and implemented over the two years of the projects.

The **final exchange meeting** held in Leuven near Brussels on October 18, 2022, where all parties met in a very engaging event, demonstrated the effectiveness of the project in involving young people. The **video** subsequently produced, both for communication and dissemination and exploitation purposes, **tells the story** from the point of view of the protagonists and provides indications to those who want to take a similar path.

2. THE DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY IN A NUTSHELL

The dissemination and communication strategy of SEEDS was aimed mainly at **teenagers** aged 13-18 who are the focus of the project. **Parents, teachers** and head teachers play a formative role in shaping teenagers' expectations and experiences, so connecting with them was key to shape the potential for future generations to improve health education and engage in STEM careers. Social workers and **health professionals**, the **private sector**, **researchers**, policy **administrators** were also important actors in the policy and implementation of the project.

2.1 Main messages

In the *Dissemination Strategy and Plan* (Deliverable 5.1) the following key messages were defined:

Messages for Teenagers

- In health and in science, the sooner, the better
- The most prevalent chronic diseases are preventable by lifestyle modification
- You have the power and the expertise to change your life.

Messages for STEM educators

- Interest in STEM can be raised by active and participative methods able to provide a meaningful direction in involvement and participation (e.g., self-directed learning, peer-based methods, co-creation of research projects, etc.). In this regard, there are countless studies, we mention, representing all of them, the research group of King's College and the Science Museum of London which proposed the approach of the [science capital](#). The purpose of this research group is precisely the relationship between participation and interest in STEM.
- Health and education are intrinsically related: improvements in education are related to better health outcomes and vice versa
- Social determinants of health and, in particular, health inequalities play a major role in health outcomes

Messages for Health and Science Education Professionals

- Citizen science is a validated method for researching in a vast range of topics and well-tailored for researching Science education and Health literacy in the community
- Citizen science research also contributes to empower communities and individuals

- Health education is a good vehicle for teaching sciences
- It is advisable to target also policy makers and managerial bodies, because they are the ones who take decisions and can have a real impact on their communities.

The previous messages were adapted according to the experience gained during the project, in particular with the makeathons.

2.2 Tools and channels

SEEDS used existing channels available to the partners and activated other appropriate ones to disseminate the previous messages. **Social media, websites, blogs**, etc. of the project and of the partners were used throughout the project.

Partners participated in a number of **events** and **conferences**, both **online** and **face-to-face**, and disseminated the project, its activities, values and results (see chapter 4.1 *Events and conferences*).

3. COMMUNICATION

According to [European Union Fund simply explained](#), **dissemination** is making sure the project's results are available to the scientific community, policy makers and industry – using scientific language prioritising accuracy. **Communication** activities, on the other hand, can be thought of as engaging various publics, creating awareness, and increasing the public visibility of the project and its results using accessible language. This could include aiming for coverage in TV, radio, print and online media.

The communication and dissemination plan was gradually adapted to the current situation and the development of the project. From March 2021 to March 2022, it was almost impossible to organise or participate in face-to-face events due to the pandemic and therefore communication was experienced almost exclusively online. As soon as it was possible and the schools were gradually reopened in the four countries of the project, face-to-face activities also resumed which culminated in the final meeting (see chapter [3.3 Final exchange meeting](#)).

3.1 Online communication

Online communication took place mainly on the site through the blog and on Twitter. On Twitter we reported the ongoing activities, published stories from the partners perspectives and interesting events in citizen science and education to engage the community and increase the SEEDS visibility.

Figure 1. Twitter followers along the project.

Figure 2. Twitter impressions.

The SEEDS website is organised into 4 sections (Blog, Events, Practical tools, Conferences and publications) in addition to the institutional part which illustrates the project, the aims and the partners. On average, we published one entry per week from June 2021 to December 2022 covering all areas of interest. Where possible, images and photos relating to the project's activities were used to make the communication more authentic.

Figure 3. The SEEDS website home page on December 6th, 2022.

3.2 Campaigns

To promote the project and above all to share results, messages and the citizen science approach in education, three communication campaigns were carried out for three audiences: a) teachers

and educators, b) social workers and health professionals and c) teens. The first two were conducted in the first half of 2022, through flashcards. The third was made with a video, a more suitable tool for reaching young people. This third campaign also represents the conclusion of the project and our legacy. See chapter [3.4 Final video](#) for the detailed description. The flashcards were translated into the languages of the participating countries.

3.3 Information material

Figure 4. The SEEDS flyer.

A SEEDS flyer were produced to present the main aspects of the project, and was handed out at two big events: the Meeting of the International Society for Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity and Living Knowledge Conference (links and details are available in chapter 4, Table 5. Events and conferences).

Table 1. CAMPAIGN A: teachers and educators. When: April 2022.

Element	Key points
Objective or goal	Make teachers and educators aware of the issue Increase knowledge
Main messages	To be defined using as much as possible the words of the teachers involved in the project, starting from the documentation available
Media	A flashcard publication to be distributed through schools, teacher associations, etc.
Spokespeople	Experts participating in SEEDS
Link	On Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/7413996#.Y5G-x-zMKko On the SEEDS website: https://seedsmakeathons.com/how-to-empower-teenagers-in-health-issues-a-practical-guide-for-teachers/

Table 2. CAMPAIGN B: social workers and health professionals. When: July 2022.

Element	Key points
Objective or goal	Reinforce knowledge Suggest an action
Main messages	To be defined using as much as possible the words of the social workers and health professionals involved in the project, starting from the documentation available
Media	A flashcard publication to be distributed through professional associations, national health organisations, etc.
Spokespeople	Experts participating in SEEDS
Link	On Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/7030852#.Y5G7L-zMKko On the SEEDS website: https://seedsmakeathons.com/how-to-empower-teens-to-manage-their-health/

Figure 5. The cover of the flashcard How to empower teenagers in health issues for teachers and educators.

Figure 6. The cover of the flashcard How to empower teenagers in health issues for health professionals.

To disseminate the communication campaigns, SEEDS used all the **existing channels** available to the partners and **activated other appropriate ones**. The following multipliers were included in the dissemination:

- EU-Citizen.Science platform
- CS and SDG conference
- ESHA (European School Heads Association, <https://www.esha.org/>)
- EUCUNET (European Children's Universities Network, <https://eucu.net/>)
- EUN (European Schoolnet, <http://www.eun.org/>)
- IPA (International Parents Association, <https://parentsinternational.org/>)
- PCST (Public Public Communication of Science and Technology, <https://pcst.co/>)
- STEM Alliance (<http://www.stemalliance.eu/>)
- TNS (Teacher Scientist Network, <http://www.tsn.org.uk/>).

3.3 Final exchange meeting

As foreseen by the Grant Agreement (M22), on October 18, 2022, the group of teens ambassadors from the different schools in Spain, Greece, the UK and the Netherlands met together with the teachers, researchers, members of the SEEDS advisory board and facilitators to share their experiences, present the interventions carried out in the schools, take stock of the project, provide recommendations for future expansions or replicas of similar initiatives. The meeting was held in Brussels and Leuven hosted in the headquarters of IMEC thanks to the hospitality of Scivil, the knowledge center of citizen science in Flanders.

The day's programme is presented below. The previous evening, Monday 17 October, the entire group met for the social dinner. In the spirit of the project, the whole event was conducted by the teen ambassadors who were the real protagonists of all phases.

Programme

Table 3. SEEDS FINAL EXCHANGE MEETING PROGRAMME | 18 October 2022.

When	What	
plenary session		
9:00-9:15	Registration of participants	
9:15-9:30	Scivil welcome	Representative of Scivil, the host organization
9:30-10:00	Ice breaker	everybody
9:45-10:15	Welcome by project lead representative: The SEEDS project in a nutshell	Rosa Maria Solà Alberich
10:15-10:55	Youth telling about their interventions	Representative of the ambassadors of the Dutch, Greek, Spanish and UK team
10:55-11:00	Introduction of the program after the break	SEEDS partners prepare for parallel sessions
11.00 - 11.30: coffee break		
parallel sessions: ambassadors split in groups to give input on lessons learned and policy recommendations		
11.30 - 13.00		
11:30-12:10	Parallel session 1 Makeathons	
12:10-12:20	Active break	
12:20-13:00	Parallel session 2 Interventions	
13.00 - 14.00: lunch and group picture SEEDS partners prepare for plenary ending		
plenary session		
14:00 - 15:00	Wrap up of the parallel sessions (15 minutes each)	A representative of each group
15:00 - 15:10	Conclusions and recommendations - How will SEEDS continue? What is still in the planning? Concluding remarks	
15:10 - 15:15	Closing statements, saying goodbye END	

Figure 7. One moment of the group work during the final exchange meeting, Leuven, 18 October 2022.

Organisation and venue

Thanks to ECSA's international collaborations with the citizen science community the final exchange meeting was hosted at [IMEC](#), the headquarters of [Scivil](#), the knowledge center of citizen science in Flanders, who generously hosted us in their beautiful buildings in Leuven near Brussels. This was also a networking opportunity that will lead to further collaborations in the future.

Several researchers/consortium members attended the Brussels exchange meeting, and all played a role in facilitating the parallel sessions.

Milou van der Zwan (City of Rotterdam, The Netherlands) and Luis Gracia (Department of Physical Education and Sports Faculty of Sport Sciences, University of Granada) — representatives of the Advisory Board — and Kunshan Goh, representative of [Health CASCADE](#), Amsterdam University Medical Center, The Netherlands, were also able to participate to the event. The illustrator [Zsofi Lang](#) documented the event with two posters.

Main conclusions

During the parallel sessions, students and teachers split into 5 groups (4 groups of students and 1 group of teachers) to discuss the makeathons and the interventions. All groups were assisted by two facilitators.

These are the main conclusions of the discussions reported during the plenary sessions in the afternoon. It is interesting that the conclusions and recommendations of students and teachers are perfectly aligned with the lessons learned recounts in D5.3 *Policy Recommendations* and the consequent policy recommendations.

Students

Main positive things:

- The possibility to create together something new and unique
- The opportunity to organise the project from the very beginning
- The opportunity to meet other people from other countries and other schools
- The trip to Brussels for the final exchange meeting
- Among the interventions, the best activities were the gymkhana and the workshop about healthy snacks
- The awareness that keeping a healthier lifestyle is important and feasible.

Things to improve:

- Engaging other people from other high schools in the interventions
- The workshop on screen time that did not work because is impossible to achieve the goals (spending less than 2 hours in front screen)
- The boring questionnaire at the beginning and at the end of the project.

Main difficulties:

Overcoming the language barriers among countries speaking different languages.

Regarding their role as ambassadors, they pointed out that they felt particularly involved in designing the posters and the activities with their peers, especially the cooking workshop. Creating ideas together with others was particularly exciting.

Keywords to summarise the SEEDS projects:

- Together as a team
- Teamwork
- Encouragement
- New friends
- Healthy
- Fun
- Activities
- Tips

- Sharing ideas.

For the future teens ambassadors would like to continue with activities such as sport day and trips and engage and motivate the students, and suggest to teachers and researchers the following:

- Finding ways to convince and motivate people
- Organising more meetings with the other countries
- Spending more time with them
- Preparing more dynamic presentations
- Doing more sport in schools and being more aware about healthy habits
- Organising more cooking workshop
- Engaging more schools
- Having more time to discuss.

Teachers

The teachers first questioned whether the SEEDS project had an impact on the lifestyle of their students. Their conclusion is that this is certainly a good start. Some elements could be improved. It would be important to deepen the gender aspects, starting from a greater knowledge of both the state of the art at the international research level and the perception of students. This would allow us to design more effective and suitable activities for everyone.

Another important aspect is the involvement of local administrations, families, other teachers and other possible stakeholders.

To be more inclusive is of the utmost importance for all teachers, they too, like students, recommend involving more schools, explaining more and better the interventions and disseminating the SEEDS approach on how to live a healthier life.

All the teachers pointed out how the COVID 19 pandemic had a great influence on the progress of the project.

Visual documentation

The illustrator Zsofi Lang was present the entire day and documented the events with two posters. The event was also documented with photos (all permissions from the students' parents were granted before the meeting) and made available on the ECSA Flickr channel with a creative commons license.

Figure 8. Visual documentation of the final exchange meeting in Brussels by Zsofi Lang.

3.4 Final video

With the multiple aim of promoting the project through the voices of the teen ambassadors, collecting the final message and distributing it to as wide an audience as possible, and leaving a legacy that goes beyond the project deadline, a video lasting about 5 minutes. The video therefore also has an exploitation value (see the deliverable 5.4 *SEEDS Exploitation and Sustainability Plan* in this regard). The [Tripwire](#) agency, which was assigned the task after careful research, has documented experience in both European project documentation and youth work.

The protagonists are the teenagers and with their voices they tell the experience and send a universal message of awareness and great determination. All partners have been interviewed and are featured in the video so that all points of view are represented: research, citizen science, policy makers.

Table 4. CAMPAIGN C: teens and the public at large. When: December 2022.

Element	Key points
Objective or goal	Empower adolescents, give them a voice Reflect on their behaviour Change attitudes
Main messages	The awareness that keeping a healthier lifestyle is important and feasible
Spokespeople	Adolescents who speak to peers
Link	https://www.youtube.com/@ecsa-europeancitizenscienc6914

Figure 9. Screenshots of the SEEDS final video. Credits to all partners and to the project are included in the cover and in the credits.

4. DISSEMINATION

4.1 Events and conferences

SEEDS representatives have been very present at important national and international events and conferences. Very different audiences were reached: operators and researchers specialised in health, citizen science or youth work, the general public, policy makers, various associations. Table 5 lists the events (21 events) with the relative number of participants (more than 5000) where available.

Table 5. Events and conferences.

Event	What	When and where	Attendees	Person and Partner
Introducing new citizen science projects launching in 2021	Webinar	May 26 2021, online	20	Famke Mölenberg (EMC)
Youth Section Meeting EMC	Presentation	June 1 2021	15	Annemieke Wargers (EMC)
Future of SciComm Conference	Poster	24-25 June 2021, Germany	40	Elisabet Llauradó, Lucia Tarro (IISPV)
Congreso de Ciencia ciudadana	Presentation	2-3 September 2021, Chile online	80	Elisabet Llauradó, Lucia Tarro (IISPV)
Connecting Communities Through Citizen Science	Online	23 June 2021	23	Claire Murray (ECSA)
Youcount Webinar	Invited talk	21 October 2021	60	Claire Murray (ECSA)
City of Rotterdam	Internal talk	18 November 2021	35	Claire Murray (ECSA), Annemieke Wargers (EMC)
Eu-citizen.science	Virtual booth	24-25 November 2021	N/A	Claire Murray (ECSA), Famke Mölenberg (EMC)
Engaging Citizen Science Conference in Denmark	Workshop	25-26 April 2022	29	Claire (ECSA)
International Society for Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity Meeting	Symposium with 3 presentations and an interactive discussion	18-21 May 2022	42	Annemieke Wargers (EMC), Famke Mölenberg (EMC), Dimitris Vlachopoulos (UOE) and Claire Murray (ECSA)

International Society for Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity Meeting	Oral presentation	18-21 May 2022	N/A	Annemieke Wargers (EMC)
Youth Section Meeting EMC	Presentation	5 April 2022	15	Annemieke Wargers (EMC)
Cross SwafS citizen science meeting	Presentation and panel discussion	13 April 2022	20	Lucia Tarro, Judit Queral (IISPV), Simona Cerrato (ECSA)
EU festival City of Rotterdam	Panel discussion	22 June 2022	20	Annemieke Wargers (EMC)
9th Living Knowledge Conference	Oral presentation	29 June 2022	20	Annemieke Wargers (EMC)
9th Living Knowledge Conference	Story telling session	29 June 2022	20	Annemieke Wargers (EMC), Katerina Polychronakis (COR), Wilma Jansen (COR), Claire Murray (ECSA)
Children's Alliance Charity	Presentation at UK Parliament	7 September 2022	180	Dimitris Vlachopoulos, Amandine Senequier (UoE)
Researchers' Night in Tarragona (Spain)	Presentation	30 September 2022	2000	Lucia Tarro, Judit Queral, Elisabet Llauradó (IISPV)
ECSA 2022 Conference – The European conference for citizen science	Presentation and panel discussion	5-8 October 2022	400	Claire Murray (ECSA)
Scientix workshop Innovative STEM Teaching Scientix workshop	Workshop	12 October 2022	20	Simona Cerrato (ECSA)
Workshop at primary school (Spain)	Workshop	9 November 2022	30	Elisabet Llauradó (IISPV)
Scientix conference	Presentation	18 November 2022	1500	Simona Cerrato (ECSA)
Workshop at Nutrition and Metabolism Master (Spain)	Presentation	25 November 2022	25	Judit Queral (IISPV)
Qualitative Research Group EMC	Internal presentation	6 December 2022	15	Annemieke Wargers (EMC)
Lecture series "Participatory Research" at the University of Salzburg	Workshop	16 December 2022	150	Claire Murray (ECSA)

4.2 Publications

The data collected and the subsequent analysis have produced a lot of material on which the researchers are working. The many articles in preparation are listed in table 6.

Table 6. List of scientific publications.

Title	Partners	Process
Clinical Trial registration https://www.clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT05002049	Responsible: IISPV Partners involved: ECSA, CoR, EMC, UoE and HUA	
International Society of Behavioural Nutrition and Physical Activity Annual Meeting Symposium	Responsible Partner: ECSA, EMC; IISPV, UoE	
SEEDS study protocol	Responsible: EMC Partners involved: IISPV, UoE and HUA	Under review
Systematic review: "Strategies to empower adolescents in healthy lifestyles by participatory-research interventions: systematic review and meta-analysis"	Responsible: IISPV Partners involved: EMC, UoE and HUA	In process
Scoping Review: "Best practices by participatory research to engage adolescents for increasing STEM interest: Scoping review"	Responsible: IISPV Partners involved: UoE	In process
Focus groups results - ambassadors	Responsible: UoE Partners involved: EMC	In process
Focus groups results – stakeholders	Responsible: EMC Partners involved: UoE	In process
Design from focus group results and implementation of Makeathons in youth of deprived areas	Responsible: ECSA Partners involved: others	In process
Interventions protocol: "Are the citizen science multicenter interventions different according to the barriers and facilitators identified? Experience of the SEEDS project, a citizen science RCT to improve the lifestyles and science engagement of youth."	Responsible: IISPV Partners involved: others	In process

Effectiveness of the interventions to improve lifestyles and science engagement in youth of deprived areas around 4 European countries	Responsible: HUA Partners involved: others	In process
Associations between types of physical activity and achieving recommended physical activity guidelines in Adolescents from Four Different Countries: A Cross-Sectional Study Using Baseline Data from the SEEDS Project	Responsible: EMC Partners involved: others	In process
Molina Ascanio M , Bilgin A S, Milanovic I, Kirsch M, Beernaert Y, Valta-Hulkkonen K, Neto V, Fiz, Filip D, Branco S, Jaakkola T, Papadakis S, Thuillier A, Cerrato S, Barouta M, Redondas J, Stojanovic I, Quarta B, Van der Niepen P, Gras-Velázquez A, (2022) <i>Innovative STEM teaching: the latest trends in STEM education, Scientix Observatory</i>	Responsible: ECSA	http://www.scientix.eu/web/guest/observatory
Claire A. Murray, Cathrine M. S. Winther, Eglė Butkevicienė, and Michael Søgaard Jørgensen, <i>Empowering youth in citizen science and citizen social science</i>	Responsible: ECSA	Proceedings of Science, 2022 https://pos.sissa.it/418/121/pdf